

<https://www.abrj.org/>

Impact Factor 2.30

Effects of Scaffolding Instructional Strategy on Students Performance and Retention in Biology among Secondary School Students in Ekiti State, Nigeria

Author's Details:

ABIDAKUN, Ojo Titus PhD and Prof FATOBA, Joseph Oba

titusabidakunoludare@gmail.com, obafato@gmail.com

Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, Ekiti State University Ado- Ekiti

Abstract:

The study examined the effects of scaffolding instructional strategy on performance and retention in Biology among secondary school students in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study ascertained the difference in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of students exposed to scaffolding instructional strategy and conventional method of teaching Biology in secondary schools. The study investigated the effects of scaffolding instructional strategy and conventional method on students' performance and retention in Biology. This study adopted a two group quasi-experimental of pre-test, post-test and control group design. The population for the study comprised 12,585 SSSII students in 205 public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The sample for the study consisted of 159 SSS II students in the selected schools using multistage sampling procedure. Two instruments used to collect data for the study, were: Biology Performance Test (BPT), Biology Retention Test (BRT). The face and content validity of the instruments were validated by experts, The reliability of the instruments (BPT and BRT) yielded reliability coefficients of 0.81 and 0.91 respectively. One research question was raised and answered while three hypotheses were generated and tested. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Research question was answered using mean and standard deviation. Hypotheses were tested using t-test. The findings of the study showed that: there was significant effect of scaffolding instructional strategy on the performance mean scores and retention mean scores of students in Biology after treatment. Based on the findings it was recommended that, implementing scaffolding as instructional strategy can significantly enhance students' performance and retention in Biology, Therefore, the use of scaffolding instructional strategy should be incorporated into the teaching approach by biology teachers.

Key words: Scaffolding, Performance, Retention

1. Introduction

Biology is a science subject which deals with the study of living organisms, The study of Biology enables man to understand the diversity of life forms, conservation and sustainable use of natural resources. Biology as a Science subject occupies a central position in the Science curriculum its inclusion as a core subject for science students cannot be de- emphasized.

The benefits of Biology for the development of any nation are too numerous to mention, and this is because Biology plays a key role in industrialization and other sectors of the economy. It serves as a pre-requisite subject for most Science and related professions like Biochemistry, Pharmacy, Medicine, Nursing, Environmental Sciences among others. According to Umoru and Onoja, (2017), the basic knowledge and skills acquired from the subject can be of great help to man and the society. The impact of Biology on the life of living organisms is wide; all ensuring that the required standard of living for both plants and animals are maintained (Ugwadu & Joda, 2015).

There is no doubt about the immense contributions of Biology to the economic growth and development of a nation. Its inclusion as a core subject for students in Senior Secondary School calls for an effective teaching using various recommended strategies. Biology as a Science subject is practical oriented subject which focuses more on knowledge application than mere knowledge acquisition, its objectives as contained in the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014) includes among others are; to equip learners with meaningful and relevant knowledge of Biology, adequate laboratory and field skills, this can be achieved through effective teaching strategies. It is observed that the performance of students' in external examinations are not encouraging, However, Umaru, (2011), Joda & Mohammed, (2017) and Joda, (2018) in their reports showed that there is a persistent low performance in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination and National Examination Council Biology examinations annually. This low performance in Biology could be attributed to poor instructional delivery approaches adopted by teachers, students' attitudinal problems, teachers' laxity towards teaching, concentration on few topics for examination purpose and students' inability to recall previously learnt materials (Umoru & Onoja, 2017).

The West African Examination Council (WAEC) chief Examiner's Report (2018) pointed out that among the factors that cause low achievement of students in Biology; poor instructional delivery approach to teaching by teachers is the most prominent factor. It observed that most Biology teachers seem not to understand other teaching strategies but hold on to the old chalk and talk method. Similarly, given students tasks seem not in vogue, few teachers that ventured into giving tasks do not mark to correct the students appropriately.

The low achievement of students in Biology at Senior Secondary Certificate Examination raises doubt about the effectiveness of current teaching approaches in use by Biology teachers. More so some topics are perceived as difficult topics by secondary school Biology students. Exposing learners to the understanding of basic concepts in Biology and achieving desirable outcomes requires the use of creative, innovative and interactive teaching approaches such as scaffolding teaching strategies which may arouse the interest of the learners, demystify difficult concepts in Biology improve their retention and performance. In addition, it is counter-productive to present ideas to learners without fully engaging them in the learning process. According to Olagunju and Akpan (2019) practical skills should be considered when taking topics in biology as it has an effect on students' skills.

Looking at the past records of Biology from West African Senior Certificate Examination from the year 2017 to 2022 indicated that there is fluctuation in the results. The number of students with grade A1 – B3 in each of the year is observed to be dwindling also the number of students with the overall grades are not encouraging compared with the total population that wrote the examination. Also, the number of students that have C4 –C6 are many which indicate that larger percentage of the students have credit passes which seems not to be adequate as they are likely to record low mark during admission process into higher institution. The number of students that have D7 –E8 and F9 seems to be larger as those in this category may not be admitted into higher institution. Generally, the results are fluctuating and not encouraging. This fluctuation in the performance of students in Biology has become an issue of great concern in recent times, however this might be as a result of teachers teaching strategies, students' attitude towards Biology, lack of adequate instructional materials among others.

Table 1: Analysis of Results of West African School Certificate Examination from 2017-2022

<i>Year</i>	<i>Total Candidate</i>	<i>A1-B3</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>C4-C6</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>D7-E8</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>F9</i>	<i>%</i>
2017	5641	1120	20	3333	59	570	10	618	11
2018	5578	1248	22.4	3389	61	466	8	475	9
2019	5563	824	15	3098	56	1069	19	572	10
2020	7161	642	9	3007	42	1719	24	1790	25
2021	6707	4765	71	1286	19	133	2	523	8
2022	7252	4230	58	1800	25	560	8	622	9

Source: Ekiti State Ministry of Education, Planning, Research and Statistics Department (2023)

The researcher observed that the fluctuation performance in the result released by West African Examination Council could be improve if new teaching methods are adopted by Secondary School Biology teacher because exposing learners to the understanding of basic concepts in Biology and achieving desirable

outcomes requires the use of creative, innovative and interactive teaching strategy such as scaffolding instructional strategy.

The term ‘scaffolding’ is derived from construction work, where it represents a temporary structure that is used to erect a building. In education, scaffolding strategy is a strategy of teaching where the teacher gives support or assistance to students in a learning situation which is tailored to the needs of the students with the intention of helping the students achieve their learning goals. The teacher gives or assigns the new tasks to students in stages and also allows the students to generate tasks and complete the tasks individually. Scaffolding instructional strategy may assist the students while learning new concept or skill in Biology this could eventually foster ability to use the knowledge acquired independently by the learners.

Scaffolding Instructional strategy may provide sufficient support to promote learning when concepts and skills are being first introduced to students. The teachers help the students master a task or a concept by providing support. These supports may include models, hints, partial solutions, think-aloud modelling, questioning, resource, compelling task, templates, coaching, guides and guidance, among others. These supports are gradually removed as students develop autonomous learning strategies, thus promoting their own cognitive, affective and psychomotor learning skills and knowledge.

Scaffolding is a teaching strategy which may provide creative ideas to individual learners and makes each interact with peers and transfer scientific knowledge. Transfer of knowledge here means knowledge gained while solving a particular problem in Biology is used to solve a likened task or used in another topic. The strategy limits the idea of teacher-centred instructional strategy where the transfer of teachers’ knowledge to students in the order. It encourages the individual learner to be more industrious and be self-confident. The activities are student centred, and students are encouraged to ask their own questions, carry out their own finding and draw their own conclusion. Brunner,(1977) stated that scaffolding involves helpful structured interaction between an adult and a child with the aim of helping the child achieve a specific goal, the purpose of the support is to allow the child to achieve higher levels of development by simplifying the task or idea, motivating the child.

Scaffolding instructional strategy is designed for students to be actively engaged ‘in doing things’ rather than in ‘learning about’ something. In doing things, the learner will not be passive; he will be a party to the provision of the solution. The learner is not only learning about what others brought as ideas, but he also brings the solution to the problem as a result of his observation, critical thinking and manipulations

Scaffolding instruction as an instructional strategy originated from Lev Vygotsky’s social-cultural theory and his concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). The Zone of Proximal Development is the distance between what children can do by themselves and the next learning that they can be helped to achieve with competent assistance (Margaret, 2018). It is the zone where instruction and learning can take place. The activities provided in scaffolding instruction are just beyond the level of what the learner can do alone. Scaffolding instruction is temporary, as the learners’ abilities increase the scaffolding provided by the more knowledgeable other is progressively withdrawn. The learner may be able to complete the task or master the concepts independently. Therefore, the goal of the educator when using the scaffolding instructional strategy is for the student to become an independent, self-regulating learner and problem solver.

Scaffolding instructional strategy of learning may help to improve students’ performance, retention, self-esteem, critical thinking and interest. It is a teaching strategy that engages and motivates the learner to learn. The strategy also reduces uncertainty, stress, frustration, surprise, discontent, test anxiety, among others. It may provide activities and tasks that will motivate or enlist the students’ interest related task; simplify the task to make it more manageable and achievable for a student.

According to Janneke, Monique and Jos (2010) scaffolding is the support given by a teacher to a student when performing a task that the student might otherwise not be able to accomplish. Aditi (2017) explained three essential features of scaffolding that facilitate learning. The first feature has to do with the interaction between the expert (teacher) and the learner. This interaction should be collaborative for it to be effective. In the second feature learning should take place in the learner’s Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). This is the zone where instruction and learning can take place. To achieve that, the expert needs to be aware of the learner’s current level of knowledge and then work to a certain extent beyond that level. The third feature of scaffolding is that the scaffold, the support and guidance provided by the expert, is gradually removed as the learner becomes more proficient.

The support and guidance provided to the learner are compared to the scaffolds in building construction where the scaffolds provide both "adjustable and temporal" support to the building under construction. The support and guidance provided to learners facilitate internalization of the knowledge needed to complete the task. This support is weaned gradually until the learner is independent. The scaffolding learning approaches become most effective when it contributes to the learning environment. Scaffolding is applied gradually, modified and finally removed according to the needs of the student.

Scaffolding strategy is a student-centred strategy which gives students more ownership of their learning, while gradually decreasing the teacher's role in the process. It also allows students to grasp the content in small chunks without being overwhelmed. Students receive guidance at the beginning of a task. Teacher support slowly decreases as students start to demonstrate mastery. Each stage allows the students to build upon the previous stage, and the teacher becomes more of a facilitator while the students become independent. Scaffolding strategy focuses on raising students' abilities one step at a time and removing support as they progress. This encourages and enables the students to be active learners in the teaching and learning process. Scaffolding begins with materials that are just a step beyond what the learners are able to accomplish unassisted. The teacher builds on the students' previous knowledge and then removes the support, allowing the learners to master the content.

Scaffolding class may allow the students to interact but not necessarily dividing into groups like collaborative strategy. Improvement in learner's performance brings about new orientation and disposition that makes Biology class interesting. When the appropriate strategy is being used by the teacher, the learners' performance may improve, and this will bring joy and the willingness to continue in the subject without being forced. Hence, their attitude towards Biology and retention may improve. The researcher hoped that students taught using scaffolding instructional strategy may perform better than those taught using the conventional strategy. Scaffolding instructional strategy may be a suitable teaching strategy that will help in alleviating the problem students' encounter in Biology.

Students' performances play a crucial role in educational system. Yusuf, Onifade and Bello, (2016) refers academic performance as a measurable and observable behaviors of a student within a specific period. In schools, student's successes are reflected in their academic performances. The academic performance is considered as a criterion to judge their total potentiality and capacities. Therefore, academic performance occupies a very important place in education and learning as well. Morgan (2010) defined academic performance as an assessment strategy by which the evidence about students' learning is gathered through students' work on a performed task. That is achievement is reflected by the extent to which skills and knowledge has been impacted to a learner.

It is observed that the performance of students in Biology is influenced by the instructional strategy adopted by teachers in secondary schools, in order to get a desirable outcomes. Biology as science is supposed to be taught using effective teaching strategy, giving credence to the above Ahmed and Abimbola (2011) opined that poor teaching method adopted by teachers at the senior secondary school level in Nigeria have been identified as one of the major factor contributing to poor performance of students in Biology. Biology as a science subject focuses more on knowledge application than mere knowledge acquisition therefore it should be taught using effective instructional strategy in order to enhanced better performance.

Conventional teaching method or traditional teaching method involving instructors and students interacting in a face to face manner in the classroom. It is a method aimed at enabling the teacher to communicate information to the learner, the common mode in this communication is the spoken word while the learners are the passive recipients. Many teachers are still teaching their students in the same manner as how they were taught and how their own teachers were taught, not much of progress in terms of the teaching perspectives (Anglin & Anglink, 2018). Transformation to these conventional methods of teaching results in fear and reluctance from teachers who find the change hard and risky.

Devinders and Zaitun (2016) cited that many teachers are still using conventional teaching classrooms while the teacher is explaining and writing on the board, students would be copying the same thing into their notes, some day-dreaming and some sleeping. Conventional teaching is also limiting room for more creative thinking and also not considering individual differences.

Retention is the ability of an individual to remember things that have been learnt or experienced after a given period of time. It appears that not every concepts taught by teachers are adequately retained by

students this may be as a result of teacher teaching strategy which seems not to be productive, this may cause student to develop negative attitude towards Biology because effective teaching and learning process depend on the varieties of methods adopted by the teachers. To support this assertion Popoola (2013) asserted that teaching methodology is a useful element in education process which enhances the teaching – learning process. She stated that there are enormous scientific and pedagogical evidence to show that students performed better in Science subjects when adequate efforts are put in place in order to improve teaching at every stage of learning therefore, effective teaching strategy such as scaffolding will assist long term memory in student and boost retention.

Retention of scientific concepts are products of teaching strategies that take into cognizance the learner-readiness which include current knowledge, stage of cognitive development and mode of intellectual functioning. Anything which aid learning could improve retention and anything that leads to confusion or interference among learned concept may decrease the speed and efficiency of learning and accelerates forgetting. Thus the success of Science teaching and learning may be dependent on the learner's ability to achieve and recall prescribed concepts meaningfully. Fatoba and Oluwatayo (2010) opined that evaluative feedback would facilitate higher retention of biological concepts, they emphasized that those students who were given immediate evaluative feedback had higher retention of biological concepts than their counterparts who were not given immediate evaluative feedback. Retention of Biological concepts could be enhance when effective teaching strategy such as scaffolding is adopted by teacher which involve active participation of students, corroborating above statement Adegbola (2016) stated that effective instructional strategy promotes long term memory in students and enhances students' performance and retention, It instills the spirit of collaboration and active participation among students, It also exposes students to experience which could ultimately help their retention and achievement.

This study investigated effects of scaffolding instructional strategy on students' performance and retention in Biology among senior secondary school students in Ekiti state, Nigeria.

2. Statement of the Problem

Biology is a practical subject that requires to be taught in a manner that the students will be actively engaged in the teaching and learning processes. It was observed that most Biology teachers in Secondary schools seems not to teach the subject by involving students in practical activities unless after they must have received instruction to practical from the examining body towards preparation for external examination. In spite of the importance placed on Biology in Science education. The report from West African Examination Council (WAEC) 2017-2022 Senior Secondary School Examination (SSCE) showed that student's performance in Biology examinations in Ekiti State appear to be fluctuating.

This fluctuating performance could be attributed to the problem of teaching strategy adopted by most Biology teachers. The researcher personal experience as a biology teacher showed that most biology teachers are used to conventional method of teaching which is teachers centered, students depend on memorization without having a complete understanding of the subject. It is also observed that Biology teacher seems not to encourage interaction and sharing of ideas among students. This perhaps serve as impediment for Biology to fully achieve its objectives.

Observations also showed that poor teaching methods adopted by teachers at Senior Secondary School in the State have been identified as one of the major factors contributing to dwindling in the performance of students over the years. It is also observed that teachers do not give tasks to the students, the persistent use of this method make students passive rather than active listeners this may not promote insightful learning and long-term retention of some abstract biological concepts.

Researcher also observed that Biology students depend on memorization of fact without understanding the basic concepts furthermore, it appears students' retention is being influenced by the teachers' disposition and teaching methods which may consequently have effect on their performance. Therefore, this study investigated the effects of scaffolding instructional strategy on students' performance and retention in Biology in Ekiti State, Secondary Schools.

3. Purpose of the Study

This study investigated effects of scaffolding instructional strategy on senior secondary school students' performance and retention in Biology in Ekiti state, Nigeria. This study specifically:

- i. examined the difference in the performance and retention mean scores of students in the experimental and control groups before treatment in Biology;
- ii. investigated the effects of scaffolding instructional strategy and conventional method on students' performance and retention in Biology;

4. Research Question

1. What is the performance of students before and after treatments in Biology?

5. Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated for this study and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the performance mean scores of students in the experimental and control groups before treatment in Biology.
2. There is no significant effect of scaffolding and conventional methods on performance mean scores of students in Biology after treatment.
3. There is no significant effect of scaffolding and conventional methods on retention mean scores of students in Biology.
- 4.

6. Population

The population for the study consisted of 12,585 Senior Secondary School Two (SSS II) students of Biology from 210 public secondary schools in the 16 Local Government Areas (LGAs) of Ekiti State

7. Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample for the study consisted of 159 SSS II students who were selected using multistage sampling procedure. The first stage involved the selection of One Local Government Area using simple random sampling technique. In stage two, four public secondary schools were selected from the Local Government Area through stratified random sampling technique using location (rural and urban) as the basis of stratification. This implied that, two schools were selected from urban and two schools from rural. In stage three, SSS II intact class of each of the four schools was used for the study.

8. Instruments

Three instruments designed by the researcher used to collect data for this study are: Biology Performance Test (BPT), and Biology Retention Test (BRT)

9. Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions were answered using mean, standard deviation and bar chart. The hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics. Specifically, hypotheses 1 - 3 were tested using t-test, All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

10. Results

Question 1: What is the performance of students before and after treatments in Biology?

In order to answer the question, the aggregate scores of students' performance in Biology test before and after the treatment were obtained for each of the groups and computed with the descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation.

The result is presented in table 2.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Showing Students' Performance in Biology before and after Treatment

Group	N	Before Treatment		After Treatment		Mean Difference
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental	86	21.7	9.93	57.2	10.21	35.5
Control	73	19.5	9.25	26.8	6.16	7.2
Grand Mean	159	20.7		43.2		22.5

Table 2 shows that before the treatment, the mean scores of students' performance in the experimental group was 21.7 while the mean scores of the control group was 19.5. The grand mean total of both groups was 20.7, suggesting that the knowledge of Biology concept in both groups were homogenous prior to the treatment. However, upon their exposure to the treatment, the grand mean total of both groups increased to 43.2 while the students taught with scaffolding had greater mean scores of 57.2 compare with the mean scores of students taught conventional methods which was 26.8. With the highest mean difference of 35.5, it could be adjudged that scaffolding had the greater potential impact on enhancing student's performance in Biology than the conventional method with mean difference value of 7.2. This further depicted in Figure iii

Fig iii: Students' Performance in Biology before and after Treatment

11. Testing of Hypotheses

Hypotheses 1: There is no significant difference in the performance mean scores of students in the experimental and control groups before treatment in Biology.

Table 3: t-test showing Differences in Students' Performance in Biology between the Experimental and Control groups before Treatment

Group	N	Mean	S.D	df	t	p-value
Experimental	86	21.67	9.925	15	1.387	0.168
Control	73	19.54	9.252	7		

$P > 0.05$

Table 3 shows that t-test was conducted to compare the performance mean scores of students in Biology for experimental and control groups. The result indicated that there was no significant difference in performance mean scores of students for experimental ($M = 21.67$, $SD = 9.93$) and control ($M = 19.54$, $SD = 9.25$; $t(157) = 1.387$, $p = .168$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected because the p-value of 0.168 was greater than 0.05 level of significance. In another word, there was no significant difference in the

performance mean scores of students in the experimental and control groups before treatment in Biology. Hence the two groups that is experimental and control groups were homogenous.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant effect of scaffolding and conventional methods on performance mean scores of students in Biology after treatment.

Table 4: t-test showing Differences in Students' Performance in Biology between Scaffolding and Conventional Methods after Treatment

Group	N	Mean	S.D	df	t	p-value
Scaffolding	86	57.2	10.21	157	22.264	.000
Conventional method	73	26.8	6.16			

P<0.05

Table 4 shows that t-test was conducted to compare the performance mean scores for experimental and control groups. The result indicated that there was significant difference in performance mean scores for experimental (M = 57.2, SD = 10.21) and control (M = 26.8, SD = 6.16; t (157) = 22.264, p = .000). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected because the p-value of 0.000 was less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there was significant effect of scaffolding and conventional methods on performance mean scores of students in Biology. This implied that the use of scaffolding instructional strategy enhances students' performance in biology than the conventional method

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant effect of scaffolding and conventional methods on retention mean scores of students in Biology.

Table 5: t-test Showing Differences in Students' Retention in Biology between the Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean	S. D	df	t	p-value
Scaffolding	86	50.2	10.09	157	14.184	.000
Conventional method	73	20.6	15.98			

P<0.05

Table 5 shows that t-test was conducted to compare the retention mean scores for experimental and control groups. The result indicated that there was significant difference in retention mean scores for experimental (M = 50.2, SD = 10.09) and control (M = 20.6, SD = 15.98; t (157) = 14.184, p = .000). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected because the p-value of 0.000 was less than 0.05 level of significance. In another word, there was significant effect of scaffolding and conventional methods on retention mean scores of students in Biology. This showed that student's retention of Biology concepts improves when using scaffolding instructional strategy than the conventional method.

12. Discussion

The study examined effects of scaffolding instructional strategy on performance and retention among secondary school students in Ekiti State. It was revealed that the performance mean scores of students in pre-test for the experimental and control group were not statistical difference. Hence the two groups were homogenous at the beginning therefore any variation noted was as a result of the treatment.

The findings from this study showed that there was no significant difference in the performance mean scores of students in the experimental and control groups before treatment in Biology. This indicates that there were no significant differences in the baseline knowledge of Biology between the experimental and control groups. Therefore, any changes observed in the post-treatment scores can be attributed to the treatment itself rather than pre-existing differences in knowledge levels. Another finding is that there was significant effect of scaffolding and conventional methods on performance mean scores of students in Biology in favour of scaffolding. This revealed that the use of scaffolding in teaching Biology resulted in significantly higher scores compared to the conventional teaching method. Students that were taught using scaffolding seems to have developed higher thinking skills which enable them performed better than their

counterparts in the conventional group this is in line with the submission of Clare 2015, which stated that students developed higher thinking skills when scaffolding occurred by an expert (teacher) or peer of higher capability. The findings indicate that scaffolding can be an effective approach for improving student performance in Biology. This is in agreement with the finding of Mohammed (2019) which asserted that students taught with scaffolding instructional strategy were more effective than the lecture method of teaching students in Biology. Also, the finding corroborates the findings of Adieze (2016) and Jibrilla (2017), who found out that students taught using scaffolding instructional strategy significantly performed better than the students in the lecture method. In a classroom interaction it is essential to use learner centered approaches like scaffolding strategy to enhanced effective teaching and learning this will motivate the students to develop interest in the subject. Therefore, incorporating scaffolding techniques into Biology instruction may lead to more comprehensive and meaningful learning outcomes for students. Also, there was significant effect of scaffolding and conventional methods on retention mean scores of students in Biology.

It is to be noted that there was significant effect of scaffolding and conventional methods on retention mean scores of students in Biology. The results indicated that students who were exposed to scaffolding strategy had higher retention mean scores compared to those who were taught using conventional methods. This revealed that scaffolding can be an effective instructional approach in improving students' retention in Biology due to students' active involvement and participation during teaching and learning process. This supports the adage which says 'what I learned I forget but what I do I remembered.' The finding is in agreement with Ibritam, Udofia, and Onweh (2015) and Adamu (2017) who found students taught with scaffolding achieved and retention higher in Biology concepts than those taught with conventional method.

13. Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, there was homogeneity prior to the beginning of the experiment in the two groups, that is, scaffolding and conventional method. The improvement recorded after the treatment could not have been by chance. It was thus concluded that the use of scaffolding instructional strategy has significant positive effect on the performance, and retention rate of students in Biology after treatment.

14. Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of this study:

1. Workshops, seminars, training and professional development opportunities should be organized for Biology teachers, to enlighten them on the use of scaffolding approach in teaching Biology.
2. Teachers should focus on creating an inclusive classroom environment that encourages active participation of the students, to enhance their performance and retention of biological concepts.
3. Biology teachers should provide additional support to students to enhance their understanding and retention of the subject matter. This can be achieved through study groups, tutoring, or other forms of academic assistance to cater to individual student's needs.

References

- Adamu, J. (2017). Effects of analogy and scaffolding instructional strategies on senior secondary school physics students' academic achievement in Adamawa State, Nigeria. Unpublished M. Tech Research Thesis. Modibbo Adama University of Technology Yola, Adamawa State.
- Adegbola, F.F. (2016). The effect of discussion and project methods on junior secondary school students' achievement and retention in Basic science in Ekiti State. *Journal of Education Ekiti State University Ado Ekiti* 6 (1) 166

- Adieze, C. (2016). Effects of edutainment, scaffolding instructional models and demonstration method on students' academic performance in Business Studies in secondary schools in Abia South Senatorial Zone in Abia State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Benchmark (Ijeb)*, 2(1), 72-84.
- Aditi, B. (2017). Effect of instructional scaffolding on high school students' academic achievement and attitude towards Science. *International Journal of Science Technology and Management*, 6(2), 228-235.
- Ahmed, M.A. & Abimbola, I.O. (2011) Influence of teaching experience and school location on Biology teachers' rating of the difficult level of nutrition concepts in Ilorin, Nigeria *Journal of Science, Technology, Mathematics Education*, 7(2), 52-61
- Anglin, L. & Anglink, K. (2018). Business education teaching and the millennial. *Conference Proceeding of Association of Academy of Business Disciplines*, 3, 26-42
- Brunner, J. (1977). The role of tutoring in problem solving. *Journal of Child Psychology*, 17(2), 89-100.
- Brunner, J. (1977). *The process of education. Revised Edition*. Harvard University Press
- Claire, M. (2015). *Scaffolding collaborative learning in mathematics classrooms: Master of interactions*. mathematics Education Research Group of Australasia. Publishes online August, 23.
- Devinder, S. & Zaitun, A.B. (2016). Mobile learning in wireless classrooms, *Malaysian Online Journal of Instructional Technology*, 3(2), 26-42.
- Fatoba, J.O. & Oluwatayo, J.A. (2010) Effects of evaluative feedback on performance and retention of secondary school students in Biology in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education Science*, 2 (1), 55-59
- Federal Republic Nigeria, (2014). *National curriculum for Science secondary school Biology*. Lagos: Government press.
- Ibritam, K.S., Udofia, N. & Onweh, V.Z. (2015). Assessing the potency of scaffolding and demonstration instructional methods on student's achievement in technical colleges in Akwa-Ibom State. *Advances in Research*, 3(1), 92- 101.
- Janneke, V., Monique, V. & Jos, B. (2010). Scaffolding in teacher-student interaction: A decade of research. *Education Psychology Review*, DO 1 10 1007/s10648-010-91227-6.
- Jibrilla, A. (2017). Effects of analogy and scaffolding instructional strategies on Physics students' academic achievement in Adamawa State. Unpublished M. Tech Thesis. Modibbo Adama University of Technology, Yola, Nigeria.
- Joda, F. M. (2018). Effect of concept mapping teaching approach on senior secondary school Biology students' achievement in Biology in Adamawa State, Nigeria. *Jigawa Journal of Multi-disciplinary Studies (JJMS)*, 1(1), 140-147.
- Joda, F.M. & Mohamed, A.A. (2017). Effect of guided inquiry teaching method on senior secondary school Biology students' academic achievement and retention in Yola education Zone, Adamawa State, Nigeria. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science, Technology and Vocational Education*, 5(1), 89-96.
- Margaret, M. (2018). What is scaffolding in teaching: Emerging perspectives on learning, teaching and technology. Scaffolding (What is scaffolding in teaching-synonym). Html

- Mohammed, A.A. (2019). Effect of scaffolding strategy on Biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary in Gombe State Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Social Science Research*, 2(5), 1-13
- Morgan, O.H. (2010). *Assessments of students' performance in Mathematics*. New York: McGraw Hill.
- Olagunju, A.M. & Akpan, E.E. (2019) Teachers Attitudes and skills As Correlates of Students Achievement in Biology in Akwa Ibom State *Nigerian Journal of Applied Psychology* S21 (1) 138-151
- Popoola, A.A. (2013). Teacher pedagogical competence. In Adegun, J.A., Babalola, J.B. and Ajayi, I.A. (Eds). *Concurrent issues in Education* 38, 496-517
- Ugwuadu, O.R. & Joda, F.M. (2015). Reality of teaching Biology in secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria. *Educational Forum A Journal of Institute of Education, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria*, 24(1), 59-75.
- Umaru, Y. (2011). Effect of instructions in metacognitive skills on self-efficacy belief, interest and achievement of low-achieving mathematics students in senior secondary school. Unpublished Ph.D Thesis. University of Nigeria (UNN).
- Umoru, E.S. & Onoja, A.I. (2017). Comparative effects of two instructional approaches on Biology students' academic achievement in evolution: Implication for curriculum review. *Journal of Curriculum Organization of Nigeria (CON)*, 1(12), 85-97.
- West African Examination Council (2018). Chief examiners report: May/June West African Senior School Certificate Examination.
- Yusuf, T.A., Onifade, C.A. & Bello, O.S. (2016). Impact of class size on learning behavioural and general attitudes of students in secondary schools in Abeokuta, Ogun State Nigeria. *Journal of Research Initiatives*, 2(1), 1-6.